

THERMOPLASTICS FOR USE IN OFFSHORE FLOWLINE APPLICATIONS

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SUMMARY

The transition from steel to thermoplastic flowlines in the offshore oil and gas industry is a paradigm shift away from tradition. The part-funded TSB consortium project 'Thermopipe' was set up to research and develop a cost effective thermoplastic composite pipeline with increased durability and reduced maintenance over corrosion resistant alloys.

Keywords: Composite material, carbon, glass, thermoplastic, sour gas, flowline, offshore, oil and gas, exposure

INTRODUCTION

Oil and gas pipelines have to operate safely and reliably under some of the most hostile environments. The combination of high pressure and temperature coupled with a cocktail of hydrocarbons, alkalis, acids, sour gas (H₂S), CO₂, etc. has a highly corrosive and erosive effect even on the most expensive corrosion resistant alloy (CRA) pipelines. Corrosion mitigation techniques including expensive corrosion inhibitors are continuously used to extend the life of the pipeline. Hydrocarbon embrittlement, sand erosion and wax hydrate build up are also issues affecting the life of steel pipelines.

In order to overcome the corrosion and reliability issues associated with steel pipelines, work has been conducted within the TSB Technology Programme part-funded consortium project, 'Thermopipe', to evaluate the use of continuous fibre-reinforced polymer composites for use in pipelines. The other partners within the Project are listed in the Acknowledgements. Currently, composite pipelines are limited primarily to use in the water and sewer industries, so this project has set out to extend the application of the materials to operate in extreme aggressive and hostile conditions of corrosive medium, high temperature (i.e. up to 150°C) and pressure (i.e. up to 400 bar) levels never experienced before by these materials.

Characterisation of Reinforced Thermoplastic Composites

Within the Thermopipe consortium, MERL has conducted a screening test programme on a wide range of thermoplastic materials under oil and gas environments, the results

of which are presented here. Material classes evaluated within the screening framework have focussed on continuous fibre-reinforced thermoplastic resin systems. Resins evaluated have included POM, PA11, PET, PEEK, PPS, PVDF, PP and PBT. Test samples were laid up with either continuous glass or carbon reinforcement depending on the resin system and the end use environment. In order to cover the range of environments that these materials might see in service, three wet environments were specified, salt water, hydrocarbon, and sour fluid (H₂S), all at representative temperatures and pressures. Three mechanical tests were selected to compare and qualify the composite systems following exposure, namely tensile, flexure and interlaminar shear testing.

Exposure	Fluid	Pressure	Temperature	Service life / Exposure period
In-Service Environment	Seawater	345 bar	20°C	15 years
Laboratory Testing	Saltwater	345 bar	40°C	1 week
			80°C	
			120°C	
In-Service Environment	Hydrocarbon gas condensate	250 bar	90°C	20 years
Laboratory Testing	Hydrocarbon gas condensate	250 bar	100°C	1 week
			120°C	
			140°C	
In-Service Environment	Production oil	315 bar	90°C	20 years
Laboratory Testing	30ppm H ₂ S, 3.9% CO ₂ , oil, formation water pH 5.3	380 bar	150	1 week

RESULTS

Option One: Saltwater

POM/Glass: The tensile and flexural property levels of POM/Glass (Figure 1) show an overall decrease on exposure to saltwater at elevated temperatures. The tensile property levels gradually decrease with increasing temperature for maximum stress and maximum strain whereas the modulus shows no change within the experimental error of

the measurement. The flexural property levels differ in that the maximum stress decreases with increasing temperature and the flexural modulus drops by approximately 70% for all temperatures. Conversely the maximum flexural strain initially increases above the unaged value but then decreases with increasing temperature.

CBT/Glass: The tensile property levels of CBT/Glass (Figure 2) show no change at 40°C, an approximate 20% drop in property levels at 80°C and a significant decrease in maximum stress and maximum strain at 120°C. The maximum strain at 120°C shows a high degree of variability, which could be due to inconsistent consolidation in the material or a breakdown of the fibre / matrix interface resulting in differing levels of water absorption between replicates. In terms of the flexural property levels, overall there is a gradual decrease in maximum stress and maximum strain at 40°C and 80°C and then a significant drop at 120°C. The flexural modulus is not affected, within the experimental error, at 40°C and 80°C but drops by approximately 90% at 120°C.

PA11/Glass: The tensile maximum stress (Figure 3) shows a high degree of variability between replicates, there is no general correlation with temperature, however there is an average property level loss of around 40%. There is no change in maximum strain within the experimental error, again the variability in the results is large. The tensile modulus shows a slight decrease with temperature. The change in flexural property levels is the same (within experimental error) for each of the elevated temperatures with a 50% drop in maximum stress, 20% drop in modulus and no change in maximum strain.

PP/Glass: The tensile properties (Figure 4) do not show a relation with temperature. There is an approximate 35% drop in maximum stress and strain on exposure to each elevated temperature. The modulus on the other hand shows a slight increase above the unaged level but is still within the experimental error. The flexural property levels do not show a significant change with temperature. The maximum strain is unaffected, and the maximum stress shows a slight decrease. The modulus shows an initial 35% drop then an increase with increasing temperature back to the unaged level.

Option 2: Hydrocarbon Gas Condensate

CBT/Carbon: The tensile maximum stress and modulus (Figure 5) show an overall decrease with increasing temperature. The maximum tensile strain however is highly variable and does not show a relation with temperature. The flexural and interlaminar shear property levels show significant deterioration with increasing temperature.

PPS/Carbon: The tensile and interlaminar shear property levels of PPS/Carbon (Figure 6) are unaffected at any of the elevated temperatures within the experimental error. The flexural properties levels are affected to a greater extent however the maximum stress and maximum strain retain up to 95% of their original value.

PVDF/Carbon: The tensile properties (Figure 7) are relatively unaffected at 100°C and 120°C however there is a marked decrease in property levels at 140°C. The flexural property levels show an initial drop followed by an increase with increasing temperature. However the variation in the results is quite large and there is no change with temperature outside of the experimental error. Overall there is a slight decrease in

flexural property levels compared with the unaged material. The Interlaminar shear property levels are unaffected within the experimental error

PET/Carbon: At 100°C the maximum tensile stress is unaffected (Figure 8) but then decreases with increasing temperature. The maximum strain however increases by approximately 20% but is not further affected by increasing temperature. The tensile modulus shows an overall decrease but with a wide variation in the results. PET/Carbon shows a reasonable retention of flexural property levels at 100°C and 120°C but not at 140°C. The Interlaminar shear property level shows an initial increase at 100°C but then decreases with increasing temperature, dropping to just 15%, of the value for unaged material, at 140°C

POM/Carbon: POM/Carbon shows (Figure 9) good retention of tensile property levels at 100°C and 120°C but disintegrated at 140°C. Similarly the flexural property levels show reasonable retention at 100°C and 120°C but show a marked drop at 140°C. The interlaminar shear property levels also show significant reduction at all elevated temperatures.

PP/Glass: Shows good retention of tensile properties at 100°C (Figure 10) but the flexural and interlaminar shear property levels have diminished significantly under these exposure conditions. At the higher temperatures the material disintegrated.

Option 3: 30ppm H₂S

PPS/Carbon: The results of the tensile testing for PPS/carbon (Figure 11) do not show a correlation with temperature. The aged samples generally retain their tensile property levels to within the range of experimental error. The results of the flexural testing (Figure 12) show an excellent retention of property levels for all temperatures. Similarly the interlaminar shear property level (Figure 13) is unaffected at all temperatures.

PEEK/Carbon: Shows good retention of tensile property levels at all of the elevated temperatures as shown in Figure 134. A good retention of flexural and interlaminar shear property levels is also shown for all temperatures (Figures 15 & 16).

DISCUSSION

Option 1: Saltwater

The effects of saltwater exposure at three elevated temperatures (40°C, 80°C and 120°C) on the mechanical property levels of four thermoplastic/glass composites are shown in Figure 1 to Figure 4. The candidate materials for this environment are POM/Glass, CBT/Glass, PA11/Glass and PP/Glass. All the materials show evidence of ageing to some extent based on the overall decrease in tensile and flexural property levels after exposure to this environment.

Water absorption in composites is more complex than in polymers alone. In the case of these thermoplastic composites, the water diffuses into the polymeric matrix, with the

extent of the absorption depending on the chemistry and morphology of the polymer as well as the volume fraction and configuration of the glass fibres.

The combination of moisture absorption and elevated temperature can cause plasticisation of the thermoplastic matrix, which allows relaxation of the polymer chains below the glass transition temperature. It also affects the residual stresses present within the composite and can allow micro-crack formation which may ultimately lead to increased water absorption, weakening of the fibre/matrix interface and development of micro-cracks. The effects of water absorption tend to become more apparent the higher the exposure temperature. This is due to the fact that the higher the temperature the faster the rate of diffusion and ultimately the higher the level of water absorption.

The mechanism of failure in all four of the materials appears to be due to deterioration of the matrix / fibre interface. As expected the unaged composite materials show brittle failure under tensile load since the load applied to the matrix is transferred to the long fibre reinforcement, which has low strain properties. However on ageing the maximum strain values decrease but the failure is no longer brittle suggesting that the load is not being effectively transferred to the fibres indicating that the matrix/fibre interface has deteriorated.

Option 2: Hydrocarbon

The effects of hydrocarbon exposure at three elevated temperatures (100°C, 120°C and 140°C) on the mechanical property levels of six reinforced thermoplastics are shown in Figure 5 to Figure 10. The candidate materials for this environment are PP/Glass, POM/Carbon, CBT/Carbon, PPS/Carbon, PVDF/Carbon and PET/Carbon. All the materials show evidence of ageing to some extent based on the overall decrease in tensile and flexural property levels after exposure to this environment.

Hydrocarbon exposure has caused more severe ageing of some of the candidate materials than others. There are similarities here with the water exposure in that the hydrocarbon is absorbed by and may chemically attack the polymer matrix. In some cases the evidence for chemical attack is clear, that is, POM/Carbon and PP/Glass samples disintegrated at elevated temperatures. For other materials the change in material properties is likely to be due to a combination of chemical and physical ageing. As with the water exposure the mechanism of failure in all of the materials appears to be due to deterioration of the matrix / fibre interface based on the change in how the testpieces fail when subjected to mechanical testing.

Option 3: H₂S

The effects of H₂S gas exposure at six elevated temperatures (150°C, 160°C, 170°C, 180°C, 190°C and 200°C) on the mechanical property levels of two thermoplastic/carbon composites are shown in Figure 11 to Figure 16. The candidate materials for this environment are PPS/Carbon and PEEK/Carbon. Both the materials show little evidence of ageing and overall show good retention of properties at elevated temperature.

CONCLUSIONS

Option 1: Saltwater

Each of the four candidate materials shows some degree of ageing on exposure to saltwater at elevated temperature. Increasing the exposure temperature allows the water to diffuse in the composites faster and may also ultimately allow a larger volume of water to be absorbed. As described in more detail in the discussion section the effect of water absorption for each of these materials has been to cause a deterioration in the matrix / fibre interface resulting in a reduction in the strength of the material. The rate of water absorption is dependent on a combination of factors including:

- the chemical nature of the thermoplastic polymer as well as its morphology in terms of, for example, crystallinity. That is, the higher the level of crystallinity the longer it takes for water to be absorbed
- the volume and configuration of fibre reinforcement
- the exposure temperature

The common factor for the four candidate materials is the service temperature which under operating conditions will be 20°C. At this relatively low temperature the water absorption is expected to be very slow and will therefore be unlikely to have a significant effect on the property levels of any of the candidate materials. In order to select two materials to go on to the long term ageing stage the materials have been evaluated in terms of their performance, ease of processing and cost, see Table 1.

Table 1: Evaluation of candidate materials

Composite	Performance	Processing	Cost
POM/Glass	✓	✓	✓
CBT/Glass	✓	✗	✓
PA11/Glass	✓	✓	✗
PP/Glass	✓	✓	✓

- CBT/glass shows good performance properties however there are difficulties with processing this material which therefore precludes it from proceeding further for this application.
- PA11/glass also shows good performance properties but it is more costly than POM or PP which show comparable performance.
- POM/Glass and PP/Glass are the materials selected for the next stage of the project comprising long term ageing.

Option 2: Hydrocarbon

Six candidate materials were exposed to a hydrocarbon environment at 100°C, 120°C and 140°C. All of the samples exhibited signs of ageing although some to a larger extent than others. Similarly to the water exposure the absorption of the hydrocarbon fluid is accelerated further as the temperature increases.

Table 2: Evaluation of candidate materials

Composite	Performance	Processing	Cost
CBT/Carbon	✗	✗	✓
PPS/Carbon	✓	✓	✓

PVDF/Carbon	✓	✓	✓
PET/Carbon	✓	✓	✓
POM/Carbon	✗	✓	✓
PP/Glass	✗	✓	✓

- CBT/Carbon shows poor performance properties and there are difficulties with processing this material which therefore precludes it from proceeding further for this application.
- POM/Glass did not survive exposure at 140°C
- PP/Glass did not survive exposure at 120°C or 140°C
- PPS/Carbon, PVDF/Carbon and PET/Carbon are the materials selected for the next stage of the project comprising long term ageing

Option 3: H₂S

Two candidate materials were exposed to a H₂S gas environment at 150°C, 160°C, 170°C, 180°C, 190°C and 200°C. Both materials exhibited good retention of properties at elevated temperature.

Table 3: Evaluation of candidate materials

Composite	Performance	Processing	Cost
PPS/Carbon	✓	✓	✓
PEEK/Carbon	✓	✓	✓

- PPS/Carbon and PEEK/Carbon are both selected for the next stage of the project comprising long term ageing

FIGURES

Figure 1 POM/Glass: Effect of one week saltwater exposure at elevated temperatures on material property levels

Figure 2 CBT/Glass: Effect of one week saltwater exposure at elevated temperatures on material property levels

Figure 3 PA11/Glass: Effect of one week saltwater exposure at elevated temperatures on material property levels

Figure 4 PP/Glass: Effect of one week saltwater exposure at elevated temperatures on material property levels

Figure 5 CBT/Carbon: Effect of one week hydrocarbon exposure at elevated temperatures on material property levels

Figure 6 PPS/Carbon: Effect of one week hydrocarbon exposure at elevated temperatures on material property levels

Figure 7 PVDF/Carbon: Effect of one week hydrocarbon exposure at elevated temperatures on material property levels

Figure 8 PET/Carbon: Effect of one week hydrocarbon exposure at elevated temperatures on material property levels

Figure 9 POM/Carbon: Effect of one week hydrocarbon exposure at elevated temperatures on material property levels

Figure 10 PP/Glass: Effect of one week hydrocarbon exposure at elevated temperatures on material property levels

Figure 11 PPS/Carbon: Effect of one week H₂S exposure at elevated temperatures on tensile property levels

Figure 12 PPS/Carbon: Effect of one week H₂S exposure at elevated temperatures on flexural property levels

Figure 13 PPS/Carbon: Effect of one week H₂S exposure at elevated temperatures on interlaminar shear property levels

Figure 14 PEEK/Carbon: Effect of one week H₂S exposure at elevated temperatures on tensile property levels

Figure 15 PEEK/Carbon: Effect of one week H₂S exposure at elevated temperatures on flexural property levels

Figure 16 PEEK/Carbon: Effect of one week H₂S exposure at elevated temperatures on interlaminar shear property levels

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